

1 Does incidental fisheries bycatch in
2 Canadian waters have population level
3 impacts for northern fulmars breeding in
4 Arctic Canada?

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16 Abstract

17 Northern fulmar (*Fulmarus glacialis*) populations breeding in Arctic Canada are vulnerable to
18 incidental seabird bycatch due to their ecology and overlapping foraging range with fisheries
19 activities. The Greenland halibut (*Reinhardtius hippoglossoides*) fishery off eastern Baffin Island,
20 Nunavut, catches fulmars incidentally in numbers that may have population-level implications for
21 this species within Canada. We provide an updated assessment of the potential impacts of
22 fisheries on fulmars that incorporates recent results from genetics, colony censuses, bycatch data
23 from fisheries in the north and farther south in Atlantic Canada, and assessments of bycatch
24 reporting error. We use Population Viability Analysis (PVA) incorporating biological removal from
25 multiple fulmar source populations with five levels of bycatch removal. We demonstrate that,
26 relative to conservatively optimistic baseline PVA models, low to average levels of probable
27 bycatch taken between two distinct fisheries regions across fulmar source populations are likely to
28 severely impede recovery or cause long-term declines of the total northern fulmar population in
29 Arctic Canada. Importantly, it was necessary to consider the cumulative impacts of both fisheries;
30 models considering fisheries separately might suggest the impact is sustainable, whereas the
31 combined impact is not. Given the high likelihood that bycatch in Canadian fisheries is having
32 negative impacts on the Arctic northern fulmar population, we suggest that targeted bycatch
33 mitigation strategies should be implemented.

34 **Keywords** conservation, population viability analysis, seabirds, sustainability, threats, VORTEX

35 Highlights

- 36 - Population viability analysis shows combined bycatch from multiple Canadian fisheries
37 hinders recovery of northern fulmar populations in Arctic Canada.
- 38 - Fisheries bycatch reporting errors lead to underestimation of fulmar population impacts.
- 39 - Bycatch mitigation strategies needed to protect northern fulmars in Canadian waters.

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42 1. Introduction

43 Globally, it is recognized that seabirds can be highly vulnerable to capture in various types of
44 fisheries gear as they spend the vast majority of their lives at sea where they acquire most of their
45 food ([1] Anderson et al. 2011; [2] Dias et al. 2019; [3] Komoroske and Lewison, 2015). Several
46 synthesis papers have identified that hundreds of thousands of seabirds are killed each year due to
47 seabird bycatch (i.e., when non-target species are caught in active fishing gear) in global fisheries
48 which can lead to negative impacts on seabird populations ([1] Anderson et al. 2011; [4] Žydelis et
49 al. 2013, [5] Phillips et al. 2024). Importantly, many reviews emphasise that the lack of data on
50 seabird bycatch is a considerable barrier to understanding the potential conservation implications
51 for seabird populations in many regions ([3] Komoroske and Lewison, 2015; [6] Waugh et al. 2008;
52 [4] Žydelis et al. 2013, [5] Phillips et al. 2024).

53 Entanglement of seabirds in active fishing gear has negative consequences both for the birds and
54 for the fishery. First, it can lead to immediate or eventual death for individual birds ([7] Brothers et
55 al. 2010; [8] Petersen et al. 2009). Second, bycatch has negative impacts on the fisheries as it can
56 lead to reductions in the target catch, and extra work for fishers who must remove live or dead birds
57 from the gear ([9] DFO, 2019; [4] Žydelis et al. 2013). Third, if enough individuals of the population
58 are killed due to bycatch, this can lead to declines in the population because the removal of
59 individuals from the populations outpaces how fast new young birds are successfully recruited in
60 each year ([10] Anderson et al. 2018; [11] Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 2019; [12] Regular et al.
61 2013). Many species of seabirds are long-lived with low annual reproductive rates (reviewed in [13]
62 Hamer et al. 2001), often laying only a single egg each year, and thus their populations can be very
63 vulnerable to large scale removals of individuals.

64 Estimating seabird bycatch rates and impacts on populations is not straightforward. Given
65 seabirds range across large geographic distances, individuals from a seabird source population
66 unit (e.g. birds from breeding colonies in a particular region) may be taken by multiple fisheries
67 management units and individually managed fisheries ([11] Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 2019).
68 Further, while fisheries effort and landings data are often highly managed, tracked, and evaluated
69 to ensure the take of individual target species are within the sustainable maximum yield for the
70 population, often data for non-target bycatch species receive much less attention. Additionally,
71 each country and jurisdiction can collect data on both fisheries effort and bycatch in varying ways,

72 and data accessibility can vary greatly ([11] Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 2019, [14] Tomasic, 2023,
73 [15] Pollet et al. 2024). Estimating the size of source populations to evaluate the relative impact of
74 bycatch removal also poses a challenge due to often significant logistical, safety, and financial
75 barriers, particularly for species that nest in remote polar locations ([16] Mallory et al. 2018). Taken
76 together, these issues all lead to challenges for analysing bycatch impacts for source populations
77 that range across multiple fishing zones.

78 The northern fulmar (*Fulmarus glacialis*) is a species of seabird that has a circumpolar distribution
79 in the northern hemisphere in both the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans, and that is potentially
80 vulnerable to bycatch across its wide range. Fulmars have slow reproduction (maximum of one egg
81 annually) and long life expectancy (average 34 years ([17] Mallory et al. 2020b), with several birds
82 banded as adults still breeding at ages likely >50 years ([18] Dunnet et. al 1991)). As part of the
83 tubenose family, along with albatrosses, northern fulmars have highly developed olfactory organs
84 that allow them to search for food at the surface of the ocean by smell ([17] Mallory et al. 2020b).
85 While this behaviour allows fulmars to forage over vast distances, it also means that fishery
86 discards being released into the environment attract fulmars to fishing vessels. As a result,
87 northern fulmars are commonly reported as incidental bycatch in both the North Pacific and the
88 North Atlantic regions ([10] Anderson et al. 2018; [19] Bærum et al. 2019; [20] Beck et al. 2021; [21]
89 Hedd et al. 2016). In Canada in particular, recent colony censuses have shown that fulmar
90 populations in the Baffin Bay - Davis Strait (BBDS) region are declining ([22] Mallory et al. 2020a),
91 and recent cumulative effects work has identified fisheries as a significant threat to the Canadian-
92 breeding population ([23] Rooney et al. 2023).

93 Northern fulmars are reported as bycatch in multiple fisheries within Canadian waters, including
94 the Greenland halibut (*Reinhardtius hippoglossoides*) fishery operating in the North Atlantic Fishing
95 Organization (NAFO) Subarea 0, (including Divisions 0A and 0B) in the BBDS region, which is
96 primarily a deep-water demersal commercial gillnet fishery ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). Notably,
97 the number of fishing boats operating in Subarea 0 in this fishery is relatively small (less than 10 in
98 any given year to date on record; [24] Knapman et al. 2023), but the small number of vessels have
99 relatively high rates of bycatch given the overall effort of the fishery ([21] Hedd et al. 2016). Farther
100 south in Newfoundland and Labrador and the Maritimes of eastern Canada, in the NAFO Subareas
101 of 2, 3, and 4, (herein referred to collectively as Subareas 234), northern fulmars have been
102 reported as bycatch in a variety of fisheries, including Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus hippoglossus*),

103 haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*), Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*), and Atlantic bluefin tuna
104 (*Thunnus thynnus*) ([21] Hedd et al. 2016, Provencher unpubl. data). Recent work has indicated
105 that reported bycatch in the Greenland halibut fishery is likely to be severely underestimated ([10]
106 Anderson et al. 2018, [25] Provencher and Mallory in review), while recent genetic studies have
107 indicated that the source populations of bycaught fulmars in these Canadian fisheries include
108 birds from the BBDS region and birds from colonies further north in the Lancaster Sound (LS)
109 region, as well as birds from European colonies ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020).

110 In light of new and emerging data on fulmar source populations and the geographic extent of their
111 bycatch, our objective was to understand whether collective incidental bycatch across multiple
112 fisheries within Canadian waters could have population level impacts for northern fulmars
113 breeding in Arctic Canada. Earlier work identified that northern fulmars in Canada were vulnerable
114 to potential population-level declines based on the best available data at the time on both the
115 population size of northern fulmars in Canada and the annual take of fulmars by the Greenland
116 halibut fishery in NAFO Subarea 0 ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). Here we aimed to update that
117 assessment using new information about fulmar colony sizes and trends ([22] Mallory et al. 2020a,
118 [27] Gutowsky et al. 2022), new bycatch reports from multiple fisheries and reporting error
119 assessments ([25] Provencher and Mallory in review, [28] Anholt et al. in review), and recently
120 developed genetic assignment tools that allow bycatch to be proportionally assigned to source
121 populations ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020). While bycatch levels in the NAFO Subarea 0 may
122 have decreased recently ([28] Anholt et al. in review), we expected that the inclusion of additional
123 mortality in our models from Canadian fisheries in other regions, combined with the recently
124 reduced population estimates of the species in Arctic Canada, would result in limited tolerance for
125 bycatch across the fisheries with unsustainable impacts on fulmar population projections at even
126 relatively low levels of probable bycatch. This exercise is particularly important for the Greenland
127 halibut fishery in NAFO Subarea 0, which has a Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) Certification
128 that recognises northern fulmar bycatch as a challenge for the fishery, and which included a
129 condition specific to northern fulmars when the fishery received MSC certification in 2020 ([26]
130 Knapman et al. 2019).

131 2. Methods

132 Here we outline how we used the best available information to create a set of Population Viability
133 Analysis (PVA) model scenarios to compare and contrast how a range of probable bycatch levels
134 across multiple Canadian fisheries may impact northern fulmar populations in Canada. We based
135 our approach on that of [10] Anderson et al. (2018), but we improved on the PVA model scenarios in
136 several ways. First, we considered bycatch taken from two distinct fulmar source populations with
137 updated estimates of colony sizes (Section 2.1). Second, we revised estimates of probable bycatch
138 removal by including more recently reported bycatch from both fisheries in NAFO Subarea 0 and
139 fisheries further south in NAFO Subareas 2, 3, and 4 in Atlantic Canada (Section 2.2.1),
140 incorporating new estimates of probable reporting error (Section 2.2.2), assigning proportions of
141 bycatch in each fishery to each source population based on new genetic information (Section
142 2.2.3), and ultimately generating a range of possible annual bycatch removal by source population
143 and fishery (Section 2.2.4). We then built baseline PVA models (i.e., without biological removal)
144 parameterized similarly to [10] Anderson et al. (2018), but updated to include more recent or
145 refined estimates of vital rates and population characteristics (Section 2.3). Finally, we ran PVA
146 models with biological removal from each of the two source populations with varying levels of
147 bycatch in each fishery Subarea, then combined outputs from both source populations to compare
148 total population trajectories.

149 2.1. Updating colony size estimates to generate starting total population 150 size scenarios for two distinct source populations of bycaught northern 151 fulmars

152 We first updated estimates of colony sizes within two distinct source populations by incorporating
153 recent census results as well as taking into account uncertainty in other outdated colony surveys.
154 In 2018 as part of the initial work to assess the potential impacts of the Greenland halibut fishery in
155 NAFO Subarea 0 on northern fulmar populations, [10] Anderson et al. (2018) used the available
156 colony size data for northern fulmars in Arctic Canada including colonies in Baffin Bay – Davis Strait
157 (BBDS) and colonies in Lancaster Sound (LS; Figure 1), as well as Greenland. This primarily
158 included colony census data collected before 2004, but the date of last colony census ranged from
159 1973 to 2010 ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). That exercise highlighted the need to update the fulmar
160 population estimate for Canada to improve population models. As a result, [22] Mallory et al.

161 (2020a) censused and reported updated colony estimates for three colonies in the BBDS region
162 that are closest to the fishing grounds of the Greenland halibut fishery in Subarea 0 (Figure 1). That
163 study found that on average the fulmar colonies in the region have declined 3-3.5% annually.
164 Therefore for this modelling exercise, we applied a -3% decline per year to project the available
165 estimates for Exeter Sound and Akpait (which have not been surveyed since 1973 and 2001,
166 respectively) to 2018. Thus, we used the updated 2018 data from Buchan Gulf, Scott Inlet, and
167 Qaqulluit as well as the projected values for Exeter Sound and Akpait to estimate the number of
168 fulmars nesting at the five colonies in the BBDS region (i.e., the BBDS source population for
169 bycatch) in 2018 as 90,598 breeding adults ($BBDS_{NEW}$; Table 1 and Table A.1).

170 While work is ongoing to update the counts for the six northern fulmar colonies in Lancaster Sound
171 (LS), recent work on assessing the trends of northern fulmars at the core monitoring site of Prince
172 Leopold Island (PLI) has shown a weak declining trend in the plot counts ([27] Gutowsky et al.
173 2022). Because of uncertainty in the colony numbers and trends for these northern colonies, we
174 present three different starting total population size scenarios (BBDS + LS) current up to 2018. We
175 chose to project all the colonies to the year 2018 (rather than 2024 when this study was being
176 conducted) as the accessible fisheries bycatch data spans 2010 to 2019; thus, this time frame
177 temporally aligns with available information for both bycatch removal and source population size.
178 The first starting total population size scenario (S1) assumes that there has been no population
179 declines at the LS colonies and uses the existing population estimates ($LS_{OLD} = 134,000$ breeding
180 adults, Table 1 and Table A.1). The second scenario (S2) assumes that the populations in LS have
181 experienced the same pressures, and have experienced the same population declines as observed
182 in the BBDS, with a -3% annual decline ($LS_{BBDS} = 81,862$ breeding adults, Table 1 and Table A.1). The
183 third scenario (S3) splits this difference and assumes that there are declines in the colonies in LS,
184 but to a lesser extent (and more similar to what has been observed at PLI; [27] Gutowsky et al.
185 2022), therefore projecting to 2018 based on a decrease in colonies of -1.5% per year ($LS_{PLI} =$
186 $104,920$ breeding adults, Table 1 and Table A.1). The 2018 values from the BBDS source population
187 ($BBDS_{NEW}$) and the three possible source population sizes for the 2018 LS region as described
188 above are summed to represent the total Canadian northern fulmar population in 2018 (Table 1).

189 2.2. Estimating annual northern fulmar bycatch removal by source 190 population and NAFO Subarea

191 When estimating the effects of bycatch on seabird populations it is common to consider various
192 scenarios that take into account the likely underestimation of reported bycatch levels ([10]
193 Anderson et al. 2018; [29] Jiménez et al. 2014; [30] Mallory et al. 2022; [31] Tuck et al. 2003). We
194 generated a range of estimates of probable annual bycatch removal by source population and
195 NAFO Subarea by first gathering the most recently reported and accessible bycatch data, then
196 incorporating new estimates of potential reporting error, and finally assigning proportions of
197 bycatch in each fishery to each source population based on new genetic information.

198 2.2.1. Reported bycatch

199 We used bycatch reported in the Department of Fisheries and Oceans (DFO) database as a
200 baseline for the minimum number of fulmars taken by fisheries in each NAFO Subarea. While at-
201 sea observers record and report on the amount of target and bycatch species in a fishery, it should
202 also be noted that the levels of at-sea observer coverage varies with the gear type, season and
203 NAFO Subarea and Division, which dictates how reported bycatch levels are scaled to represent
204 the fisheries' total estimated take of a species ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). The main fishery around
205 the BBDS fulmar colonies is for Greenland halibut in NAFO Subarea 0, which primarily uses
206 demersal gillnets typically set at depths greater than 300 m ([24] Knapman et al. 2023). The gillnets
207 are baited with squid ([32] Bayse and Grant, 2020), a primary prey item for northern fulmars ([33]
208 Mallory et al. 2010), and offal is often discarded after hauling in nets, which is also highly attractive
209 for the birds. The fishery operates in most years from May to November, with reported bycatch of
210 fulmars having high inter-annual variation ([28] Anholt et al. in review). Earlier reports from DFO on
211 fulmar bycatch in the Greenland halibut fishery in NAFO Subarea 0 reported an average of 212
212 individuals taken in each year when assessed from 2010 to 2015 ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). Here
213 we used the more recently updated reported bycatch of northern fulmars in Subarea 0, which
214 ranged between 10 and 325 individuals per year when the data was assessed from 2010 to 2019
215 ([28] Anholt et al. in review). Importantly, a missing piece from previous fulmar bycatch impact
216 assessment work was the inclusion of bycatch in other Canadian fisheries that killed Canadian
217 breeding fulmars outside of the Arctic (i.e., outside of Subarea 0 in NAFO Subareas 234; Figure 1).
218 An ongoing project assessed all fisheries reporting northern fulmars as incidental bycatch in the
219 Canadian NAFO Subareas 234 between 2010 and 2019, including in gillnets and longlines of the

220 Greenland halibut and Atlantic bluefin tuna fisheries (Provencher unpubl. data). Thus, here we
221 used reported bycatch values from years when data were available (2010-2015) for these fisheries
222 in NAFO Subareas 234, which ranged between 220 and 2300 fulmars taken on an annual basis
223 (Provencher unpubl. data).

224 2.2.2. Bycatch reporting error rate

225 We derived a range of possible bycatch reporting error rates for adjustment of reported annual
226 bycatch values to represent a range that covers known reporting error values, as well as scenarios
227 that assume additional errors that are not quantifiable at this time, including species
228 misidentification and unobserved mortality. The Greenland halibut fishery in Subarea 0 has several
229 different limitations within its data that may contribute to underestimation of the number of
230 individual fulmars that are removed from the population in any given year. First, errors can arise in
231 seabird bycatch estimates based on the data collection method used in the field ([7] Brothers et al.
232 2010). Recent work by [25] Provencher and Mallory (in review) used three different bycatch data
233 collection methods, all carried out by at-sea observers in the Subarea 0 Greenland halibut fishery,
234 and found clear discrepancies between methods (at-sea observers either reporting data in the DFO
235 database or using enhanced seabird datasheets, and a carcass collection program between a
236 university and industry partners). [25] Provencher and Mallory (in review) found that bycatch
237 reported in a given year when using alternative methods can be as much as 11x greater than that
238 which is reported in the DFO database, suggesting that the minimum bycatch levels reported in the
239 bycatch database used for assessing bycatch levels may substantially underestimate the number
240 of seabirds caught by a fishery on an annual basis. In addition to this quantified reporting error rate,
241 the at-sea observer DFO data reports several species of shearwaters that are not found as far north
242 as reported in the bycatch data ([10] Anderson et al. 2018). Due to the similarities between
243 procellariid species (the family that includes both shearwaters and fulmars), and based on carcass
244 collections from the fisheries ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020), it is likely that all procellariids
245 reported in the database are northern fulmars. Finally, only dead birds brought on board are
246 counted in the Subarea 0 Greenland halibut fishery bycatch dataset. When birds are entangled in
247 gear and released alive, severe injuries from the nets or handling can lead to eventual death. Dead
248 birds that are lost from the nets before being hauled on board are also not counted in the at-sea
249 observer data. Using enhanced seabird bycatch collection data sheets, [25] Provencher and
250 Mallory (in review) found that in one year, while 35 birds were reported dead, an additional 24

251 fulmars were caught in the gear and released alive. Thus, we ran model scenarios with varying
252 bycatch reporting error rates that ranged from 1x to 15x, to capture known reporting error values
253 (up to 11x), as well as a feasible range of higher values up to 15x.

254 2.2.3. Source population genetic assignment factor

255 Using recently developed genetic tools, we developed Subarea-specific genetic assignment factors
256 based on the proportions of bycatch taken in each fishery assigned to each of the source
257 populations. Fulmars collected or caught away from the breeding colonies can be assigned to a
258 breeding colony or region based on matching genetic markers ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020).
259 Initial work using genetic colony assignment tools identified that 30% of the northern fulmars
260 caught in the Labrador Sea (NAFO Subarea 2) were from colonies in Arctic Canada, and 100% of
261 the fulmars caught in Subarea 0 were from Arctic Canada ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020). More
262 recent on-going work expanding the number and geographic range of the colonies (including
263 Greenland, Iceland and Norway) included as potential source populations have further refined
264 these estimates. This work indicates that of the fulmars caught as bycatch in the Subarea 0
265 Greenland halibut fishery, 10% are actually from Greenland colonies, while 80% are from BBDS
266 colonies and 10% are from LS colonies (based on samples from PLI and Cape Vera, Akpait and
267 Qaqulluit; V.L. Friesen, Queen's University, pers. comm.). Furthermore, 40% of the fulmars
268 collected in Subarea 2 in the Labrador Sea are from colonies in the Canadian Arctic, with a roughly
269 equal split of the birds from the BBDS and LS regions (V.L. Friesen, pers. comm.). Based on these
270 findings, we used a genetic assignment factor for fulmars taken in Subarea 0 of 0.1 for LS take and
271 0.8 for BBDS take, and for fulmars taken in Subareas 234 of 0.2 for LS take and 0.2 for BBDS take.

272 2.2.4. Simulated annual northern fulmar bycatch by source population and 273 NAFO Subarea

274 We used a simulation-based approach to estimate a relevant range of annual northern bycatch
275 rates of fulmars from the LS and BBDS source populations for Subarea 0 and Subareas 234 for use
276 in our PVA models. We multiplied the range of reported Subarea-specific bycatch by the range of
277 probable reporting error rates, and adjusted for Subarea-specific genetic assignment to each of the
278 source populations. For fulmars taken in Subarea 0, we simulated 10,000 potential annual bycatch
279 values from each source population by randomly generating a value from a truncated negative
280 binomial distribution parameterized based on reported bycatch values and fit using maximum

281 likelihood estimation (mean (μ) = 127.7, size parameter (θ) = 0.966, lower bound = 10, upper bound
282 = 325) for total fulmar bycatch, multiplying by a random bycatch reporting error rate multiplier
283 between 1x and 15x (assuming a uniform distribution), then multiplying by a genetic assignment
284 factor of 0.1 for LS take and 0.8 for BBDS take. A negative binomial distribution was chosen rather
285 than a Poisson distribution due to the observed positive skew of reported annual bycatch values,
286 and then truncated to the lower and upper bounds to prevent generated values falling far outside of
287 the observed range. Similarly for fulmars taken in Subareas 234, we simulated 10,000 potential
288 annual bycatch values from each source population by randomly generating a value from a
289 truncated negative binomial distribution parameterized based on reported bycatch in Subareas
290 234 (μ = 845, θ = 1.854, lower bound = 220, upper bound = 2300) for total fulmar bycatch,
291 multiplying by bycatch reporting error rate multiplier between 1x and 15x, then multiplying by a
292 genetic assignment factor of 0.2 for LS take and 0.2 for BBDS take (Figure 2).

293 From these distributions of simulated bycatch values, we determined five potential levels of fulmar
294 take for each fishery Subarea and source population (in addition to modeled scenarios with zero
295 bycatch) as minimum, low (first quartile), mid (median), high (upper quartile) and maximum
296 bycatch levels (Figure 2). Simulated potential annual fulmar bycatch in Subarea 0 from LS ranged
297 from 1 – 488 individuals, with a median of 57, and in Subarea 0 from BBDS ranged from 8 – 3,900
298 with median of 458 (Figure 2). Similarly in Subareas 234, simulated annual fulmar bycatch from
299 each of LS and BBDS ranged from 44 – 6,900 individuals, with a median of 1,058 (Figure 2).

300 2.3. Population Viability Analysis

301 Using our updated source population sizes and simulated annual northern fulmar bycatch levels by
302 fishery Subarea and source population, we modelled population dynamics by conducting
303 Population Viability Analysis (PVA) under varying bycatch and starting population size scenarios
304 using the software VORTEX (Version 10.6.0.0; [34] Brook et al. 2000; [35] Lacy and Pollak, 2023).
305 VORTEX uses vital rate estimates (e.g., survival, productivity, breeding propensity) and population
306 characteristics (e.g., age distribution, age at first reproduction, brood size, and carrying capacity,
307 along with initial population size and removal rates from harvest or bycatch mortality) to simulate
308 population trajectories through a time series of stochastic demographic and environmental events
309 ([35] Lacy and Pollak, 2023). We parameterized our VORTEX models similarly to [10] Anderson et al.
310 (2018), with some modifications based on more recent or refined reported estimates of vital rates
311 and population characteristics (see details in Appendix B of the Supplementary Material, Table

312 B.1). We built our PVAs as population-based models tracking a single population projection with
313 1,000 iterations of population dynamics evaluated over three generations, as per guidelines from
314 the International Union for Conservation of Nature for evaluating population viability in long-lived
315 species ([36] IUCN, 2000). Because our demographic parameterization and thus life tables differ
316 slightly from that used in [10] Anderson et al. (2018), our generation time also differs; [10] Anderson
317 et al. (2018) derived a generation time of 21.85 years for both sexes and we derived 23.56 years for
318 females and 26.49 years for males. Our values align with a more recently published estimate of
319 25.3 years for both sexes ([37] Bird et al. 2020); however, we elected to project our models for the
320 same duration as [10] Anderson et al. (2018) for easier comparison, resulting in 66-year projections
321 at a 1-year time step, assuming a stable age distribution at time $t=0$; which is just short of three
322 generations given the updated generation times.

323
324 We first built PVA baseline models for each source population with a basic model set-up without
325 bycatch in either NAFO Subarea. Because we have two distinct source populations, BBDS and LS,
326 with a single potential starting population size in 2018 (i.e. N at $t=0$ or N_0) for BBDS (BBDS_{NEW}) and
327 three potential starting population sizes for LS (LS_{OLD}, LS_{BBDS}, and LS_{PLI}; Table 1), each PVA model
328 set-up is run four times, resulting in simulated population trajectories for each potential source
329 population N_0 . We then modelled the population trajectory implications for the two source
330 populations of different possible levels of bycatch in each fishery Subarea, using identical
331 demographic inputs to the baseline models and an additional Subarea-specific bycatch take
332 parameter for each source population, held constant over the 3-generation population projection
333 (see details in Appendix C of the Supplementary Material, Table C.1). For all PVA models with
334 bycatch removal, we set birds to be vulnerable to bycatch mortality in their first year of life onward,
335 where subadults (i.e., pre-breeders) and adults (i.e., breeders) are equally susceptible to bycatch
336 mortality, as [10] Anderson et al. (2018) showed that a skewed bycatch ratio towards subadults
337 made little impact on population trajectories. This implies the age distribution in the bycatch is
338 proportional to the age distribution in the population. We considered PVA model set-ups with the
339 remaining 35 possible combinations of the five fulmar bycatch levels between Subarea 0 and
340 Subareas 234, as well as zero bycatch in either Subarea 0 or Subareas 234. Again, each model set-
341 up resulted in four PVA models, one for each potential source population N_0 , with the bycatch take
342 parameter for the source population set to the total take between the two NAFO Subareas. This
343 resulted in four sets of 36 model set-ups for a total of 144 PVA models (Table C.1).

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Using our 144 PVA model outputs, we compared stochastic exponential population growth rates (r) for each source population under varying starting source population sizes (N_0 for BBDS_{NEW}, LS_{OLD}, LS_{BBDS}, and LS_{PLI}) and bycatch level combinations to examine how varying bycatch levels in each NAFO Subarea impacted LS and BBDS independently. We derived median r and estimates of uncertainty for each model from the distribution of r across the 1,000 model iterations. The r value for each iteration represents the long-term r for that particular simulated population as it is derived as the arithmetic mean of the instantaneous r at each time step; uncertainties in r therefore represent uncertainties across iterations, not across years. We also compared total population trajectories and total % change over three generations ($\Delta_{3\text{GEN}}$) for LS and BBDS combined under the three starting total source population scenarios (Table 1) to identify thresholds at which bycatch would cause rapid decline in our simulated populations. For each model, we generated 1,000 estimates of total N_t for each source population scenario by summing values of N_t at each time interval from paired iterations, allowing for illustration of the projected total source population trajectories over three generations accounting for stochasticity, as median total N_t with 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs; all calculated as highest density continuous intervals). It should be noted that summing values across paired iterations assumes that demographic and environmental stochasticity are operating independently between the two source populations. We believe this is a valid assumption given the foraging ranges of these source populations likely have limited overlap during the breeding season, and weather conditions and ice dynamics experience high variation both within and between LS and BBDS ([38] Gaston et al. 2005, [39] Grumet et al. 2001, [40] Shen et al. 2021, [27] Gutowsky et al. 2022). In general, we present results (i.e. r , $\Delta_{3\text{GEN}}$, N_t) as medians with 95% CIs to consider confidence in the direction and magnitude of estimates without assumptions of the underlying distributions. Full output and derived rates for all 144 PVA models is provided in Appendix C of the Supplementary Material (Table C.1).

370 3. Results

371 3.1. Population growth rates for two source populations at various 372 potential initial population sizes and bycatch levels

373 The baseline PVA models with zero bycatch for four starting source population sizes (N_0 for
374 $BBDS_{NEW}$, LS_{OLD} , LS_{BBDS} , LS_{PLI}) resulted in slow but steady growth with median r values of 0.0075 -
375 0.0076 with lower 95% CI between 0.004-0.005 and upper 95% CI of 0.01 (Figure 3, Table C.1). All
376 PVA results presented subsequently are relative to these conservative hypothetical baseline
377 models (see *Supplemental Information - PVA Demographic Parameterization* for details).

378 For BBDS, r remained positive at simulated min to mid bycatch levels in Subarea 0 if bycatch in
379 Subareas 234 was min or low (Figure 3). If mid level bycatch occurred in both Subarea 0 and
380 Subareas 234, the BBDS population declined (i.e., r becomes definitively negative). High bycatch in
381 Subareas 234 caused declines for BBDS regardless of the bycatch level in Subarea 0, even with no
382 birds taken annually. High bycatch in Subarea 0 caused population growth to stop (i.e., 95% CI of r
383 overlaps zero) if Subareas 234 bycatch level was min or zero, and population declines for BBDS if
384 bycatch in Subareas 234 was low or more. Max levels of bycatch in either Subarea caused
385 population extinction within three generations (100% of model iterations reached $N = 0$ before N_{66}),
386 regardless of bycatch levels in the other Subarea, as did high bycatch in both Subareas (Figure 3,
387 Table C.1).

388 For LS, the variation in r across the three N_0 possibilities was considerable, but all were more
389 resilient than BBDS across bycatch levels below max in Subareas 234 because fewer birds are
390 taken from LS in Subarea 0 compared to BBDS (Figures 2, 3). Max levels of bycatch in Subareas 234
391 caused population extinction for all three LS N_0 scenarios, even with zero bycatch taken in Subarea
392 0 (Figure 3). If the LS population hasn't changed since the last surveys (LS_{OLD}), r continued to be
393 positive (i.e., population growth occurred) with the addition of min to high bycatch in Subarea 0 and
394 min to low levels of bycatch in Subareas 234 (Figure 3). If bycatch taken in Subareas 234 from LS_{OLD}
395 is mid to high, r becomes negative regardless of bycatch levels in Subarea 0. If the LS population
396 has declined at BBDS rates (LS_{BBDS}), r was positive with the addition of min to mid levels of bycatch
397 in Subarea 0 and min to low in Subareas 234 (Figure 3). Like LS_{OLD} , if bycatch in Subareas 234 is mid
398 to high, r becomes negative regardless of bycatch occurring in Subarea 0. The major difference

399 between PVA results from LS_{OLD} and LS_{BBDS} is that r is negative in LS_{BBDS} if bycatch in Subareas 234 is
400 low and bycatch in Subarea 0 is high, and r at LS_{BBDS} decline if bycatch in Subarea 234 is mid and
401 Subarea 0 is max (Figure 3). Population growth rates in LS_{PLI} were intermediate between LS_{OLD} and
402 LS_{BBDS} , with the primary difference being more similar r to LS_{OLD} at high Subarea 0 and low Subareas
403 234 bycatch levels in that r remains positive, and at max Subarea 0 and mid Subareas 234 bycatch
404 levels in that r 95% CI overlaps zero (Figure 3).

405 3.2. Total population projections and changes over three generations at 406 various bycatch levels

407 For all three total population size scenarios, max levels of bycatch in Subareas 234 caused certain
408 extinction/extirpation of Canadian Arctic northern fulmars within 30 years or less (i.e., $\Delta_{3GEN} = -$
409 100%; Figure 4). Similarly, high bycatch levels in Subareas 234 or max levels in Subarea 0 caused
410 long-term total population declines (i.e., $\Delta_{3GEN} < 0$) regardless of the level of bycatch in the other
411 Subarea (Figure 4). Min or low bycatch levels concurrently in both Subareas did not result in
412 definitive long-term decline in any total population size scenarios (i.e., $\Delta_{3GEN} > 0$; Figure 4).

413 Under the best case scenario for total population size in 2018 ($S1 = BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{OLD}$), low bycatch
414 levels in Subareas 234 and mid bycatch in Subarea 0 did not substantially hinder long-term
415 population growth relative to baseline (i.e., $\Delta_{3GEN} > 25\%$; Figure 4). If bycatch reached mid levels in
416 both Subareas, long-term population increase was impeded ($\Delta_{3GEN} \leq 0$; Figure 4). Under the worst
417 case scenario ($S2 = BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{BBDS}$), Δ_{3GEN} remained positive if bycatch was min in Subareas 234
418 and at a high level or lower in Subarea 0 (Figure 4). Mid levels of bycatch in Subareas 234 inhibited
419 long-term total population increases or caused losses at all levels of bycatch in Subarea 0,
420 including zero. If bycatch levels in Subarea 0 were high or max and Subareas 234 were mid or
421 higher, the total population experienced severe long-term losses ($\Delta_{3GEN} < -25\%$). The implication of
422 bycatch removal under the moderate scenario ($S3 = BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{PLI}$) were intermediate between S1
423 and S2, with the main difference being medial resilience to mid bycatch levels.

424 4. Discussion

425 We modelled the potential population-level impacts of seabird bycatch on Canadian northern
426 fulmars by fisheries in both NAFO Subarea 0 and Subareas 234, with the ultimate objective of

427 informing fisheries management in Canada. We used updated fulmar demographic and census
428 information ([22] Mallory et al. 2020a) combined with an improved understanding of the geographic
429 extent ([26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020) and magnitude of bycatch ([25] Provencher and Mallory in
430 review), and the assignment of bycaught birds to distinct source populations ([26] Colston-Nepali
431 et al. 2020), to demonstrate that probable average levels of bycatch take between the fisheries
432 Subareas are likely to cause declines and impede recovery in northern fulmars in Arctic Canada at
433 the current reported fishing and bycatch levels. Unmitigated bycatch at feasible average current
434 levels would most certainly lead to substantial declines, while complete population crashes are
435 likely under the highest simulated bycatch levels, reflecting a scenario with high rates of bycatch
436 under-reporting coupled with fisheries expansion beyond the current fishing effort. Managing these
437 Canadian fisheries using an holistic ecosystem approach will require careful consideration of
438 these potential impacts of incidental bycatch on seabird populations, with vigilant monitoring of
439 the health and status of northern fulmar colonies.

440 When interpreting our PVA results, it is critical to keep in mind that the fate of each simulated
441 population is conditional on our baseline growth assumptions under zero bycatch, which are
442 undoubtedly conservative (see Appendix B for details). We derived the carrying capacity of the
443 populations in our baseline model relative to the State of Canada's Birds (SOCB) 2024 population
444 goal, which is set based on maximum historical estimates of population sizes ([41] Environment
445 and Climate Change Canada and Birds Canada, 2024). In the case of the fulmar, these historical
446 estimates are complicated to interpret given that they are from a period when fisheries discards
447 were widely available and possibly augmenting the diet of fulmars in the North Atlantic ([42] Fisher
448 1952). On the one hand, unmitigated discarding by fisheries in the past may have also caused
449 higher levels of fulmar bycatch, but on the other hand where gear known to be associated with high
450 bycatch vulnerability would have been used (e.g., gillnets were commonly used for cod and salmon
451 fisheries in the North Atlantic, [43] Tull et al. 1972; longlines continue to be used in many regions,
452 [44] Løkkeborg 1998, [45] Dietrich et al. 2009), fulmars would have been negatively impacted by
453 expanded fisheries in the past. Unfortunately, these unknowns about past population parameters
454 cannot be derived from current or past data, but are important to consider when interpreting model
455 outputs. Additionally, our derivation of mortality for the 0 to 1 age class is likely an underestimate
456 as we selected the input value based on the first-year survival rate which resulted in definitively
457 positive growth, all else being equal. It follows that our simulation results should not be interpreted
458 as prescriptive in that a specific number of birds taken as bycatch would lead to population growth

459 or declines, but rather that particular magnitudes of bycatch are sufficient to overcome any
460 robustness of a plausible positive growth model, given our baseline population growth rate is
461 possibly a conservative overestimate.

462 It is important to remember that we have chosen the baseline model based on parameters that
463 ensured population growth was occurring, which may or may not be the base population
464 parameters given the level of ecological change the oceans are experiencing (e.g., [46] Vihtakari et
465 al. 2018, [47] Ingvaldsen et al. 2021, [48] Ahme et al. 2023). Fulmar populations experience
466 multiple threats during the breeding season and when south away from their colonies ([23] Rooney
467 et al. 2023), and while we chose the optimistic baseline model of increasing populations, we did
468 not account for any other threats in our bycatch removal models. These other threats must be
469 considered when looking holistically at broader conservation perspectives and ecosystem-level
470 implications. For example, we also know that northern fulmars in Canada were exposed recently to
471 the recent outbreak of avian influenza, and experienced at least some mortality associated with the
472 virus ([49] Giacinti et al. 2024; [50] Erdelyan et al. 2024). In the absence of being able to incorporate
473 other threats within our modelling, our results show that fisheries as a single factor can cause
474 population-level declines in Arctic fulmar numbers. Thus from a conservation perspective, it is
475 critically important that these results be considered within the larger context (e.g. climate change
476 affecting food webs, emerging diseases, disturbance; see review by [2] Dias et al. 2019).

477 Earlier demographic modelling work by [10] Anderson et al. (2018) set out to demonstrate the range
478 of possible impacts of fisheries bycatch given numerous uncertainties surrounding model inputs,
479 and identified several additional data gaps in that process with partners. We expanded on this work
480 by reducing many of these uncertainties and filling some of these gaps. First, this earlier work
481 considered bycatch in Subarea 0 only, from different “source populations” relative to colony
482 distance from the Subarea 0 fishery (considering colonies within 200 km (three colonies in BBDS),
483 within 500 km (same three colonies in BBDS plus west Greenland), or all colonies in BBDS, LS, and
484 west Greenland combined), and population sizes of the local source populations were based on
485 older census data which most certainly overestimated the size of the Canadian colonies. Our
486 simulations indicated that total annual fulmar bycatch from both Canadian Arctic fulmar source
487 populations and all NAFO Subareas combined could range from 97 – 18,188 individual birds across
488 all bycatch level combinations, with a median number of fulmars taken annually of 6,403 birds. Our
489 results highlight the importance of accounting for bycatch of birds from multiple source

490 populations across multiple fisheries zones (e.g., [51] Lewison and Crowder 2003); ignoring
491 bycatch in Subareas 234 severely underestimates the impacts of bycatch in Subarea 0 on the total
492 Canadian Arctic fulmar population, and vice versa, to the extent that it could be assumed bycatch
493 rates were sustainable when they were in fact slowing population growth and inhibiting population
494 recovery or even causing rapid declines.

495 The source population of bycaught fulmars was previously unknown, and thus [10] Anderson et al.
496 (2018) spread bycatch evenly amongst the colonies contributing to the total initial population size.
497 In light of genetic work that was inspired by these first findings, we are able to assign bycatch by
498 fisheries in Subarea 0 and Subareas 234 to either the BBDS or LS population, providing improved
499 insight into how bycatch in Canadian fisheries could impact the Canadian fulmar population. The
500 distribution of the bycatch between these two source populations in separate PVA models greatly
501 influenced the ultimate impact on the population as a whole, and highlights how genomics studies
502 can inform population modelling exercises (e.g., [52] Seaborn et al. 2021, [53] Hohenlohe et al.
503 2021). Without this genetic assignment information, our model parameterization would have
504 followed previous work and assumed equal take from the regions, leading to potential
505 underestimation of the effects in the BBDS area, but an overestimation of the effects in the LS area.
506 The differential bycatch pressure the colonies experience, as highlighted through the genomics
507 work, also illustrates how seabird populations that are widely geographically dispersed can face
508 varying pressures (e.g., [54] Bustnes et al. 2015), which is important to consider when assessing
509 population-level impacts and when devising mitigating actions.

510 Given the high likelihood of seabird bycatch in NAFO Subarea 0 and Subareas 234 causing declines
511 in the Arctic northern fulmar population, targeted seabird bycatch mitigation strategies should be
512 considered. A critical aspect of this consideration is evaluating how different mitigation
513 approaches may affect all bycaught seabird species. Strategies may include changing fishing gear
514 types, night setting, and centre hull hauling. In the Atlantic region, northern fulmar bycatch is
515 reported in both gillnet and longline fisheries ([21] Hedd et al. 2016, [55] Mallory et al. 2006),
516 demonstrating that the species is vulnerable to both types of gear when they are present in the
517 region. This is important to consider as the fisheries in NAFO Subarea 0 consider how to manage
518 bycatch levels of several species simultaneously as one gear type may reduce the bycatch of one
519 species, but it may increase the bycatch of another vulnerable species. These considerations are
520 critical in applying a holistic ecosystem approach to fisheries management.

521 Despite bycatch reports of northern fulmars in Arctic Canada being numerically relatively low, no
522 matter how few individuals appear to be reported as bycatch, the only means of assessing whether
523 'it matters' at the population level is to compare that removal relative to the size of the source
524 population ([10] Anderson et al. 2018; [11] Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 2019; [30] Mallory et al.
525 2022). But the total potential impact of a fishery on a seabird population can only be examined if
526 the total number of birds killed across all vessels active in the fisheries are considered ([11]
527 Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. 2019). Key to our findings was considering multiple scenarios of total
528 population size in light of uncertainty around temporal change in the LS colonies. In the absence of
529 current colony census information, we elected to incorporate uncertainty in our approach. Our
530 results highlight that the Arctic northern fulmar population in Canada may be resilient to relatively
531 low levels of bycatch concurrently in both fisheries Subareas, but that mid level bycatch, especially
532 in Subareas 234, substantially impeded recovery or caused declines regardless of whether the size
533 of the LS colonies has remained the same as historical estimates or has declined at the same rates
534 as the BBDS colonies. Additionally, high levels of bycatch in Subareas 234 or max levels in either
535 Subarea led to rapid rates of decline, and in many cases, total extirpation of fulmars from Arctic
536 Canada within three generations. At these relatively high, but plausible, levels of bycatch, the lower
537 annual bycatch rates from LS in Subarea 0 are insufficient to offset the losses in BBDS, leading to a
538 collapse of the entire simulated population.

539 Accurate bycatch data from fisheries is notoriously challenging to collect, obtain, and analyse due
540 to the often biased nature of the data, which reduces its utility for informing our understanding of
541 potential impacts on seabird species that are vulnerable to bycatch ([56] Good et al. 2022).
542 Additionally, at the individual vessel level, the number of observed fulmars caught in the gear in any
543 given year may be low (from singles to tens), and therefore fishers may not recognize bycatch levels
544 as problematic. Further, collecting seabird demographic and census data can face significant
545 logistical, safety, and financial barriers, particularly for species like northern fulmars that nest in
546 remote and generally inaccessible locations, particularly in Arctic Canada ([16] Mallory et al. 2018).
547 While we have carried out several studies with partners to gain a better understanding of key
548 knowledge gaps (e.g. [26] Colston-Nepali et al. 2020; [25] [22] Mallory et al. 2020a), there are still
549 various unknowns in the interactions between fisheries and fulmars. Future work should explore
550 how different model types that incorporate uncertainty in the underlying data may be used to refine
551 estimates of the population level impacts of fisheries bycatch on fulmars.

552 5. Conclusion

553 For Arctic Canada, the Greenland halibut fishery has an existing condition on their MSC
554 certification that states the fishery is ‘expected to maintain or not hinder rebuilding of northern
555 fulmar at/to levels which are highly likely to be within biologically based limits or to ensure that the
556 UoA [Unit of Assessment] does not hinder their recovery’ ([26] Knapman et al. 2019). Importantly,
557 the potential impact on seabird populations from fisheries cannot be assessed in the absence of
558 reliable fishery bycatch and seabird population data, and cannot be fully understood without
559 considering mortality from multiple fisheries in concert with relative impacts on bycaught source
560 populations. Thus, in northern Canada, there is an ongoing need for critical evaluations of bycatch
561 using both fisheries and seabird data within an ecological model to understand if this condition is
562 being met by the Greenland halibut fishery given the multitude of pressures on the fulmar
563 population. Indeed, our PVA simulations suggest that even if bycatch by the Greenland halibut
564 fishery in Subarea 0 were reduced to zero, continued bycatch at average levels or higher in
565 Subareas 234 will impede fulmar recovery, and in the most extreme case, lead to collapse of
566 fulmars in the Canadian Arctic. Critically, we have only incorporated bycatch in Canadian fisheries,
567 yet Canadian breeding northern fulmars range beyond Canada’s jurisdiction in the non-breeding
568 season ([57] Lyngs 2003, [58] Mallory et al. 2008), and are vulnerable to bycatch from fisheries in
569 the non-breeding range (e.g., [59] Darby et al. 2023). Our cautiously optimistic baseline PVA model,
570 combined with the fact that our source populations face additional and cumulative threats beyond
571 those considered here ([23] Rooney et al. 2023), suggests that bycatch of Canadian Arctic northern
572 fulmars in Canadian fisheries must be addressed to avoid significant ecological impacts.

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578

579 **Data Availability**

580 All data used in the analysis are reported or referenced in the manuscript.

581 **CRedit authorship contributions statement**

582 **SE Gutowsky:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing -
583 original draft, Writing - review and editing. **A Morrill:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology,
584 Validation, Visualization, Writing - review and editing. **HL Major:** Conceptualization, Writing –
585 review and editing. **ML Mallory:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing –
586 review and editing. **CM Francis:** Conceptualization, Writing – review and editing. **JF Provencher:**
587 Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Writing - original draft, Writing – review and
588 editing.

589 **Declaration of competing interests**

590 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
591 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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763

764 **Tables**

765 Table 1. Three starting total population size scenarios for the two Arctic northern fulmar bycatch
 766 source populations in 2018, derived from colony-specific projections (see Figure 1, Table A.1). The
 767 number of individuals across all age classes was derived using the stable age distributions of the
 768 fully parameterized PVA baseline models.

Starting total population size scenario	Number of breeding adults (BBDS + LS = total)	Number of individuals across all age classes (BBDS + LS = total)
S1: $BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{OLD}$	$90,598 + 134,000 = 224,598$	$139,826 + 206,811 = 346,637$
S2: $BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{BBDS}$	$90,598 + 81,862 = 172,460$	$139,826 + 126,343 = 266,169$
S3: $BBDS_{NEW} + LS_{PLI}$	$90,598 + 104,920 = 195,518$	$139,826 + 161,930 = 301,756$

769

770 Figures

771 Figure 1. Arctic northern fulmar colonies in relation to NAFO Fishery Subareas 0, 2, 3 and 4 where
772 fulmars from two source populations, Lancaster Sound and Baffin Bay – Davis Strait, are bycaught
773 in the Greenland halibut and bluefin tuna fisheries.

774 Figure 2. Range of potential annual northern fulmar bycatch by NAFO Subarea and fulmar source
 775 population derived from 10,000 simulations based on a range of known reported annual fulmar
 776 bycatch in each Subarea, probable bycatch reporting error, and proportional genetic assignment
 777 correction factors for each fishery Subarea and source population. Plots show the distribution of
 778 potential total number of individuals taken per year in NAFO Subarea 0 from the Lancaster Sound
 779 (LS) source population (A) and from the Baffin Bay – Davis Strait (BBDS) source population (C), and
 780 in NAFO Subareas 2, 3, and 4 from each of the LS and BBDS source populations (same proportional
 781 take from each; E), and how these distributions arise from a range of bycatch reporting error rate
 782 multipliers from 1x to 15x (B, D, F). Vertical lines and labels depict five levels of fulmar bycatch
 783 considered in PVA models: minimum, low (first quartile), mid (median), high (third quartile), and
 784 maximum bycatch level.

785 Figure 3. Simulated median population growth rate (r) under varying combinations of bycatch levels
 786 in NAFO fisheries Subarea 0 and Subareas 234 derived from PVA models for four initial source
 787 population sizes (N_0): A) Baffin Bay – Davis Strait (BBDS) and B-D) three potential N_0 scenarios for
 788 Lancaster Sound (LS; see Table 1). Bycatch levels are shown with the simulated number of birds
 789 taken as bycatch in each Subarea from the respective source population in brackets. Bycatch level
 790 combinations resulting in estimates of r with 95% confidence intervals (CI) overlapping zero are
 791 indicated by an open circle. Bycatch level combinations resulting in population extinction within
 792 three generations in >95% of model iterations are indicated by an “X”.

814 Figure 4. Population trajectories (A, C, E) and simulated median percent change (Δ_{3GEN} ; B, D, E) over three generations under different total starting population size scenarios (by
 815 row, see Table 1), and varying combinations of bycatch levels in NAFO fisheries Subarea 0 and Subareas 234. We generated 1,000 estimates of total N_t for each source population
 816 scenario by summing values of N_t at each time interval from paired iterations of PVA models to visualise projected total source population trajectories accounting for stochasticity
 817 and independent biological processes and bycatch pressure on each source population, shown on the left as median total N_t (solid line) with 95% high density confidence
 818 intervals (shared areas). On the right, bycatch level combinations resulting in estimates of Δ_{3GEN} with 95% confidence intervals (CI) overlapping zero are indicated by an open
 819 circle, and combinations resulting in population extinction within three generations ($\Delta_{3GEN} = -100\%$) are indicated by an "X".